

Copper(II)—Fluorescein Complex

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Cu(II) fluorescein complex isolated from an aqueous medium has the composition $\text{Cu C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5 \cdot 3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Ir, uv-vis diffuse reflectance, and esr spectral studies, magnetic and thermal measurements have been made to characterize the complex.

FLUORESCEIN (disodium salt), one of the widely used laser dyes¹ can coordinate through carboxyl, phenolic and carbonyl oxygens. The mercury complex of fluorescein is known for its antiseptic properties², while Cu(II), Zn(II) and Co(II) complexes have been studied for their antibacterial activity³. Recently some complexes of fluorescein with Cu(II), La(III), Ce(III), Sm(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Fe(II), Fe(III), Mn(II), VO(IV)⁴ and UO₂(VI)⁵ have been reported. These have been isolated from ethanolic media.

It has been observed here that the isolation of many of these complexes is possible from an aqueous medium. The Cu(II) complex is now being described which is different from that obtained by Bhobe⁴, in an ethanolic medium. The characterization has been done by ir, uv-vis reflectance and esr spectra, and by magnetic and thermal studies.

Experimental

Preparation: The complex was obtained as a brown precipitate on mixing aqueous solutions of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and fluorescein (disodium salt) in the ratio 2:1 respectively, using AnalaR grade BDH reagents. The pH of the supernate was ~3.5. The precipitate was filtered, washed several times with water and dried at 120°.

Analysis: Found: C, 52.41; H, 3.97; Cu, 13.75 per cent. Calcd. for $\text{CuC}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5 \cdot 3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: C, 52.52; H, 3.72; Cu 13.91 per cent.

Spectra: Ir spectra were recorded on Grating-Infrared-Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer Model 577 using KBr pellets.

Uv-vis reflectance spectra was obtained on a manual reading spectrophotometer.

Derivative of the esr spectrum was recorded on a Varian V-4502-12 esr spectrometer with a 100 Kc/sec modulation unit. DPPH was used as g marker.

Magnetic Measurements: Susceptibility measurements were done by Faraday method using Mettler Analytical Balance.

Thermal Studies: Tga results were obtained on a thermobalance (make-F.C.I., Sindri) at a heating rate of 10° per min.

Results and Discussion

Composition, Colour and Solubility: The complex has a formula $\text{CuC}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5 \cdot 3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ arrived from analytical data. It is quite different from those obtained by Bhobe⁴, which have hydroxo-bridging groups besides the fluorescein ligands. The brown colour of the complex and its insolubility in all common organic solvents such as ethanol, chloroform, carbontetrachloride, ether, n-hexane, benzene and nitrobenzene and very low solubility in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide suggest its polymeric nature.

Thermal Analysis: The tg curve of the complex shows that the weight is constant upto 80° followed by a slow loss in weight upto 220°. A total loss of 13.0 mg (for a 219.5 mg sample) corresponds to the loss of 1.5 mole H_2O , which is loosely associated.

The weight is then constant between 220-260°, beyond which rapid decomposition of the complex occurs. This decomposition occurs in two stages (i) From 260° to 360° total loss is 64.5 mg which corresponds to loss of $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and C_6H_5 . From this it may be inferred that these two water molecules are in coordination sphere of the complex. Hence the formula is $[\text{CuC}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. (ii) Weight is again constant from 360° to 420°. Decomposition starts once again and continues up to 780°, the residue remaining being 48.0 mg. For many Cu(II) complexes with organic ligands, it has been reported⁶ that residue contains a mixture of CuO and CuCO_3 . In the present case, the residue corresponds to an equimolecular mixture of CuO and CuCO_3 (or basic carbonate), as has been reported in the case of copper-quinaldate complex⁶.

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Magnetic Moment : The observed μ_{eff} value is 2.11 BM, which is in the normal range (1.7-2.2) for copper(II) complexes.

Ir Spectra : Important ir frequencies of the ligand are compared with those of the complex (Table 1). Tentative band assignments are also given.

TABLE 1—INFRARED ABSORPTION BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF FLUORESCIN AND THE COPPER(II) COMPLEX

Assignment	Ligand	Complex
Water	3300-3400 (b,w)	3390 (b,m)
$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	1678 (b,m)	—
$\delta(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	1634 (w)	1636 (m)
$\nu(\text{COO}^-)$ assym.	1598 (s)	1580 (s)
$\nu(\text{COO}^-)$ sym.	1382 (s)	1390 (s)
$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}^-)$	1310 (s)	1325 (s)

Carbonyl absorption present in the ligand at 1678 cm^{-1} as a broad band of medium intensity is altogether absent from this region in the complex and is shifted to lower frequencies where it gets overlapped with COO^- asymmetric band.

COO^- asymmetric and symmetric bands show shifts after complexation and the difference between the two decreases. $\text{C}-\text{O}^-$ frequency at 1310 cm^{-1} moves to 1325 cm^{-1} on complexation⁷.

As the ligand is hygroscopic, therefore, very broad but weak band in region $3300-3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to water (as moisture) is noted. In the complex a very broad but intense band at 3390 cm^{-1} is probably due to coordinated and lattice water⁸. The band at $\sim 1635 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is probably due to $\delta\text{H}_2\text{O}^9$.

Electronic spectra : As the ligand is coloured therefore, reflectance spectra of the ligand and the complex have been studied.

λ_{max} for the ligand is at 530 nm and this is shifted to 500 nm on complexation. In addition to the ligand band other absorption bands (of Cu(II) ion) are also obtained and are given in table 2 with their tentative band assignments.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION SPECTRUM OF $\text{Cu C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_8 \cdot 3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (DIFFUSE REFLECTANCE)

λ (nm)	ν (cm^{-1})	Assignment
290 (λ_1)	34480	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$
650 (λ_2)	15380	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{7g}$
775 (λ_3)	12900	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$

As discussed by Bannister and Cotton¹⁰, the spectral data favour square planar geometry, which is further substantiated¹¹ by the ratio $\lambda_2/\lambda_1 = 2.24$.

Esr : First derivative of esr gives two g values as $g_1 = 2.0557$ and $g_{11} = 2.2984$ and line width is 349.7 gauss. g_1 comes out to be 2.1366. From the values of g_1 and g_{11} it may be inferred that $dx^2 - y^2$ is the ground state¹² which is in conformity with band assignments in electronic reflectance spectrum.

Theoretical computation of susceptibility using the following spin only expression

$$\chi_{\text{Theor}} = \frac{N}{M} g^2 \beta^2 S(S+1)/3kT$$

gives the value $3.20 \times 10^{-6}/\text{gm}$, whereas observed value of

$$\chi_{\text{obs}}^{\text{corr}} = 4.135 \times 10^{-6}/\text{gm}. \text{ Since the observed value}$$

is higher, it may be inferred that orbital contribution is there, which the above spin only formula does not take into account.

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